

Research

Effectiveness of Integrating Hands-On Activities In The Learning of Chemical Bonding in High-School Setting

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Abstract: This research work sought to improve the perception, attitude and conceptual understanding of students, through the use of hands-on instructional approaches in chemical bonding. The final year general art four (4) Students of John Evans Atta- Mills Senior High School numbering 50 was the sample used for the study. The research instruments used included observation, interview, questionnaires and tests. It was observed that these students believed that, the content of chemical bonding is difficult and boring, also the concept was always taught without practical activities (hands-on activities) hence the wrong perception and low conceptual understanding of students which facilitate no attempt to excel in the subject. The students were engaged in hands-on activities, group work and constant use of teaching and learning materials to develop and sustain their interest in the subject. It was deduced that the lack of activities involving learners affected their conceptual understanding and performance in integrated science. It is hoped that learners will be more engaged in the teaching and learning process through the use of hands-on activities to help change their perceptions, improve the conceptual understanding and also to develop and sustain their interest in the subject matter.

Introduction

The importance of education in general and integrated science education in particular to mankind cannot be over-emphasized. No nation can afford to overlook integrated science education at any level of education and hope to thrive in any field of human endeavor. Science education is imperative for useful living in any society. It is at the center for producing resources necessary for socio-economic, scientific and technological development needed for advancement of any nation. Training young scientist require knowledgeable, dedicated and resourceful science teachers to lay good foundation of science. The importance of science has enable governments to design policies to increase science learning in schools. Unfortunately despite the government's drive to draw more students to science, especially at the second cycle levels, more students keep running away from it (Eminah, 2007).

O'Connor (2002) identified the use of inappropriate teaching strategies as one of the factors that contribute to the low participation and performance of students in integrated science. The teaching methods used are not practical enough and that teachers make little effort to relate the concepts learnt and the examples/illustrations used to real life, especially within the context of the students' own lives and their immediate environment. This has a negative effect on students' interest and motivation to study integrated science, mathematics and technology (SMT) subjects. Danso (2010) stipulated that teachers favor teacher-centred, knowledge based teaching methods that leave little room for learners' participation. The most commonly used teaching methods at both basic and secondary levels have been found to be lecturing; question and answer; explanations of procedures and note giving, in that order (O'Connor, 2002).

Hands-on activities in learning

In school science teaching, ideas need to be presented in ways that are both authentic representations of the scientific concepts, and yet simple enough to be meaningfully understood by the learners. The teaching of chemistry involves the development of more effective and scientifically aligned strategies to teach high-school students the key concept of chemical bonding. According to Teichert and Stacy (2002), this attempt is motivated by many studies conducted worldwide that revealed that the traditional approach of teaching bonding is problematic. More specifically, during the last two decades, researchers have found that students lack a deep

conceptual understanding of the key concepts regarding the bonding concept and fail to integrate their mental models into a coherent conceptual framework (Bodner & Domin, 1998; Taber 2001).

Ekwueme, Ekon & Ezenwa-Nebife, (2015) stated that, Hands-on-approach is a method of instruction where students are guided to gain knowledge by experience. This means giving the students the opportunity to manipulate the objects they are studying, for instance, plants, insects, rocks, water, magnetic field, scientific instruments, calculators, rulers, mathematical set, and shapes. In fact, it is a process of doing mathematics and science where students become active participants in the classroom.

Several studies in the literature show that hands-on activities help students to outperform students who follow traditional, text-based programmes (Turpin, 2000). Hands-on activities enhance students understanding and replace their misconceptions with the scientific ones (Ünal, 2008), develop students attitudes toward science positively (Bilgin, 2006) and encourage their creativity in problem solving, promote student independence, improves skills such as reading, arithmetic computation, and communication. Lebuffe (1994) emphasized that children learn better when they can touch, feel, measure, manipulate, draw, and make charts, record data and when they find answers for themselves rather than being given the answer in a textbook or lecture.

Ekwueme, Ekon and Ezenwa-Nebife (2015) posit that hands-on learning approach is learner-centered and involves the child in a total learning experience which enhances the child's ability to think critically. It is obvious therefore, that any teaching strategy that is skewed towards this direction can be seen as an activity-oriented teaching method (Hands-on-approach). Through hands-on-approach, students are able to engage in real life illustrations and observe the effects of changes in different variables. It offers concrete illustrations of concepts and improves students' academic achievement in learning. Obanya (2012) in his convocation lecture confirmed the above statement by adding that the average retention rate of learning by lecture is 5% while that of practice by doing (Activity-oriented) is about 75%. It can be seen that retention rate increases progressively with the use of more interactive and activity-oriented teaching methods. On the contrary, Ekwueme and Meremikwu (2010) observed in their study that some teachers object to the use of interactive activity-oriented method stating that it is time consuming and do not permit total coverage of the syllabus.

Hands-on activities use real objects to compliment multiple modes of communication, linking visual learning to what is being said and discussed (Lee, Penfield & Maerten-Rivera, 2009). Hands-on activities enable students to discuss debate, verbalize and explain processes and concepts while working together. An observation of hands-on learning noted that students' demonstrated strong communication tied to working in teams (Bass, Yumol, & Hazer, 2011). Bass, Yumol and Hazer (2011) opined that with the right kind of planning and presentation, hands-on teaching can restore focus and spark engagement. An independent observation of teachers using hands-on learning noted that students were enthusiastic and generally stayed on-task during guided hands-on activities. It has been demonstrated that students who are disadvantaged economically or academically gain the most from activity-based programmes (Bredderman, 2012).

Significance of the study

Bonding is a core concept in chemistry teaching, and therefore a thorough understanding of it is essential for understanding almost every other topic in chemistry such as carbon compounds, proteins, polymers, acids and bases, chemical energy, and thermodynamics (Hurst, 2002). According to Robinson (2003) bonding is considered by teachers, students, and chemists to be a very complicated concept of chemistry. The concepts associated with chemical bonding and structure, such as covalent bonds, molecules, ions, giant lattices, and hydrogen bonds are abstract and in order to understand these concepts, students must be familiar with mathematical and physical concepts that are associated with the bonding concept such as electronic configuration, valency, orbitals, electronegativity, and polarity. It is in the light of the challenges learners encounter in learning chemical bonding that has triggered the researcher to investigate the effectiveness of integrating hands-on activities on SHS 3 students in the learning of chemical bonding in chemistry.

METHODOLOGY

Study design

The study was an action research which sought to find solution to the students' challenges in the conceptual understanding of chemical bonding. The sampling size was fifty (50) and comprised of thirty (34) male and sixteen (16) female students of a Senior High School in the central region. The Researcher adopted a purposive sampling technique because all the members of the science

classes had some difficulty with chemical bonding. The main instruments used to collect data was a Class Test. Pre-test was conducted to discover the challenges students encounter in chemical bonding while post test was conducted after the implementation of intervention strategies. This was supplemented with questionnaire. The test items were validated by an expert (a senior Lecturer) at the department of integrated science education of university of Education,, Winneba. This was done to ensure that the content of the questions were valid and reliable for testing.

Administration and Collection

The intervention strategy designed to obtain detailed information about students' concepts in ionic or electrovalent and covalent bonds through hand on activities is outlined below.

- i. With the help of periodic tables students indicated the following information on index cards: element symbols (only the first 20 elements), atomic number, atomic mass, state of matter, atomicity and element type.
- ii. Grouping elements written on index cards as metals and non-metals.
- iii. Writing Lewis dot structures of elements and compounds on sheets and on index cards.
- iv. Calculation of electronegativity difference and stating covalent bonds as polar and non-polar.
- v. Using models kit construction of compounds to improve conceptual understanding on chemical bonding.
- vi. Cardboard drawings showing ionic or electrovalent bonds and covalent bonds as well as writing formula for compounds and molecules.

After the treatment, ten multiple choice questions were administered and the maximum time required for the test was 15 minutes. At the end of 15 minutes, the papers were collected from the students by the researcher and assessed using the prepared marking scheme. Each of the tests (pre-test and post-test, see appendix A and appendix B) consisted of 10 questions and the total score allocated was 20 marks. Students were however observed and interviewed during the treatment period to determine the extent to which the use of hands on activities have shape their attitudes toward the learning of chemical bonding and improved their conceptual understanding.

Data analysis

The results obtained from the study were put into frequency table with the number of people scoring within each group expressed as a percentage and used for analysis. Descriptive statistics

such as mean and standard deviation as well as inferential statistics (correlation and t-test at 95% confidence level) were computed to establish the relationship between pre-test and post –test scores.

Results and Discussion

Table 1: The two tailed t-test for independent sample analysis for pretest and posttest

DATA SCORES							
Test	No	Mean	SD	Df	R	t-value	p-Value
Pre-test	50	11.80	2.30	29	0.67	-6.32	1.9×10^{-6}
Post-test	50	15.63	2.40	29	0.67	-6.32	1.9×10^{-7}

*= significant; $p < 0.05$

Mean gain=3.83

A= Not significant, $p > 0.05$

Table 1 shows that, the mean score obtained by students at the pre-test was 11.80 (SD = 2.30) while that of the mean score for the post test was 15.63 (SD = 2.40). Statistical analyses showed that students scored significantly higher ($t = -6.32$; $p < 0.05$) at the post-test than at the pre-test. The result also showed that there was a gain of 3.83 from the mean scores of the post-test and pre-test which also confirmed that the treatment had significant influence in students' conceptual understanding as well as performance. This overall gain can be associated to the effectiveness of the intervention strategy employed. The present study support the findings of Ekwueme, Ekon and Ezenwa-Nebife (2015) that used hands on activity to improve students' performance in mathematics and basic science. Similarly, Turpin, 2000 reported that learning via hands-on activities are more effective than learning in traditional method in the area of science achievement.

Table 2: Students response to questionnaire after treatment

No.	Items	YES (%)	NO (%)
1	Did you obey the activity procedure	46(93.3)	4(6.7)

2	Did you follow activities easily	38 (80)	12(20)
3	Did you enjoy the lesson	44(90)	6(10)
4	Did you get the concepts of the lesson by doing the activities	36(76.7)	14(23.3)
5	Was there student-student interaction during the lesson	44(90)	6(10)
6	Did the teacher acts as a guide	42(86.7)	8(13.3)
7	Did the teacher has the primary role in delivering the content	40(83.3)	10(16.7)
8	Did the method increase your interest to read chemistry	46(93.3)	4(6.7)
9	Can you explain your answers with confidence	36(76.7)	14(23.3)
10	Do you prefer activity oriented teaching to lecture teaching without activity	40(83.3)	10(16.7)

Table 2 shows that 93.3 % (46) and 80% (38) of the respondents were able to practice hands-on activity procedure and followed it easily respectively. This was because the researcher used simplified English which was easy to read and understand. However, key terms necessary to enhance their conceptual understanding was not compromised. Among the respondents 90 % (44) indicated that they enjoyed the hands-on oriented teaching. In a follow up interview a section of the respondents stated that, conducting hands-on activities makes lesson more exciting and not boring which leads to positive motivational outcomes. This agrees with the findings of Franklin and Peat (2005) who concluded that hands-on learning provides a more realistic and exciting experience of the content.

Again, 76.7% (36) of the respondents grasped the concepts of the lesson by doing the activities. This means that hands-on practice has the capacity to engage students, makes them critical thinkers and improve their cognitive skills of learning and hence improve on conceptual understanding. Also, 90% (44) of the respondents indicated that the hands-on practices enabled them to interact with other students during the lesson while the teacher assisted them to develop concepts relevant to the lesson. Similarly, an observation of hands-on learning noted that students' demonstrated

strong communication tied to working in teams (Bass, Yumol, & Hazer, 2011). Group learning enables good students to assist the weak students in the class thereby making the class more lively and productive.

In the study, 93.3% (46) of the respondents indicated yes to agree that hands-on learning increased their interest to pursue chemistry. According to Hidi and Renninger (2006), interest is an important variable in the school context, as it can influence students' levels of learning, their academic performance and the quality of their learning experience. In the study 76.7% (36) of the respondents were bold that they can explain their answers with confidence while 83.3% (40) of the respondents indicated their preference to activity oriented teaching (hands –on doing). In an interview, respondents stated that hands-on doing facilitates conceptual understanding and recalling of chemical bonding concepts. In a similar study, Ateş & Eryilmaz, (2011) indicated that students who experienced hands-on activities frequently (every day or once a week) had significantly higher scores of science achievement than those students who experienced hands-on science infrequently.

Conclusion

The Hand-on activities carried out in the study were writing of chemical symbols and atomic number of elements on index card, grouping of elements into metals and non-metals, writing Lewis dot structure, drawing of electronic configuration, drawing diagrams for ionic bonds and covalent bonds, using tag of war to explain the concept of polarity, modelling with ball and sticks as well as calculation of electronegativity difference. All these activities employed in the study significantly facilitated conceptual understanding and improved students' performance in the learning of ionic and covalent bonds. Again, Hands-on activities made lesson more interesting, engage students, enable them to interact with colleagues, build their confidence, makes them critical thinkers, problem solvers and improve their cognitive skills of learning and leads to positive motivational outcomes. Students demonstrated positive attitude towards hands- on learning and many of them enjoyed hands- on teaching.

Recommendations

- Hands- on teaching activities must be well planned and evaluated to achieve teaching objectives

- Teachers must supervise and guide students to develop concepts during lessons. It should be noted that some students are likely to play with teaching materials and might not follow presentation of content.
- Teachers must also try to allocate reasonable time for each hands-on activity in other not to waste a lot of time on only one activity.
- Teachers should emphasize on synchronizing the theoretical lessons into practical, this will give the student broad view about the application of their respective courses/majors
- Teachers should be specific with their teachings in terms of notifying the students their aim of each class lessons and what they plan to achieve- this will make a daily progress in the students educational lives

APPENDIX A PRE-INTERVENTION TEST

Circle the correct option that completes the sentences below.

1. Hydrochloric acid has a (an) _____ bond and its chemical formula is _____.
 - a) covalent, HCl
 - b) ionic, HCl
 - c) covalent, HCl

2. When a Na atom loses an electron, it gets a charge of _____.
 - a) -1
 - b) +1
 - c) 0

3. The process of joining atoms together is called _____.
 - a) ionization
 - b) bonding
 - c) Atom affinity

4. The chemical formula of the product formed from the reaction between Mg and Cl is _____.
- a) MgCl_2
 - b) MgCl
 - c) Mg_2Cl
5. In an electrovalent bond, electrons are _____ or _____.
- a) lost or gained
 - b) Shared
 - c) none of the above
6. In a covalent bond, electrons are _____.
- a) lost or gained
 - b) shared
 - c) distributed
7. An atom that has lost or gained electrons becomes a (an) _____.
- a) Anion
 - b) Cation
 - c) ion
8. Negatively charged atoms are called as _____.
- a) Protons
 - b) Electrons
 - c) ions
9. Dative covalent bond is formed between atoms of _____.
- a) Metals
 - b) non-metals
 - c) metals and non-metals

10. N has 5 valence electrons and it is diatomic. How many covalent bonds are there in a N₂ molecule?

- a) Single
- b) double
- c) triple

APPENDIX B

POST INTERVENTION TEST

Circle the correct option that completes the sentences below.

1. How is the bond in N₂ different from the bond in KCl?

- a) N₂ is covalent and KCl is ionic
- b) N₂ is ionic and KCl is ionic
- c) N₂ is ionic and KCl is covalent

2. Calcium Oxide is a (an) _____ compound and the formula for Calcium Oxide is _____.

- a) covalent, CaO₂
- b) ionic, CaO
- c) ionic, CaO₂

3. Nitrogen has 5 valence electrons and it is diatomic. How many covalent bonds are there in an N₂ molecule?

- a) single
- b) double
- c) Triple

4. The bond formed when Na combines with Cl is _____.

- a) ionic
- b) covalent
- c) metallic

5. Anions tend to _____ electrons to become _____ ions.

- a) lose, positive
 - b) gain, negative
 - c) lose, neutral
6. Cations tend to _____ electrons to become _____ ions.
- a) lose, positive
 - b) gain, negative
 - c) lose, neutral
7. Calcium Chloride is a (an) _____ compound.
- a) metallic
 - b) covalent
 - c) ionic
8. Write the chemical formula for a compound that has one Calcium atom and 2 Chlorine atoms. Predict the bond between them.
- a) CaCl_2 , ionic
 - b) CaCl_2 , covalent
 - c) Ca_2Cl , ionic
9. Ionic bond are formed between atoms of _____ and _____.
- a) metals and non-metals
 - b) Metals
 - c) non-metals
10. From the list of elements given, select 2 elements that would likely form an ionic bond.
- a) K, Cl
 - b) Ar, Cl
 - c) K, O

References

- i. Ateş, O., & Eryilmaz, A. (2011). Effectiveness of hands-on and minds-on activities on students' achievement and attitudes towards physics. *Asia-Pacific Forum on Science Learning and Teaching* , 12 (1), 1-22.
- ii. Bass, K. M., Yumol, D., & Hazer, J. (2011). *The Effect of Raft Hands-on Activities on Student Learning, Engagement, and 21st Century Skills.*" RAFT Student Impact Study. Retrieved January 24 , 2012, from <<http://www.raft.net/public/pdfs/Rockman-RAFT-Report.pdf>>.
- iii. Bilgin, I. (2006). The effects of hands-on activities incorporating a cooperative learning approach on eight grade students' science process skills and attitudes towards science. *Journal of Baltic Science Education*, 1(9), 27-37.
- iv. Bodner, G., & Domin, D. (1998). Mental models: The role of representations in problem solving in chemistry. Paper presented at International Council for Association in Science Education. *Summer Symposium, Proceedings*.
- v. Bredderman, T. (2012). Effects of Activity-based Elementary Science on Student Outcomes: A Qualitative Synthesis. *Review of Educational Research*, 53(4), 499-518.
- vi. Danso, J. B. (2010). Evaluation of inclusive education practice in Ghana: Survey of inclusive pilot schools. Thesis submitted to the Department of Educational Foundation, Faculty of Education, University of Cape Coast, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award .
- vii. Eminah, J. K. (2007). The alignment of J.H.S curriculum prescriptions and classroom practice. *Journal of Alternative Development and Area Studies*, 26(3), 73-101.
- ix. Ekwueme, C. O., Ekon, E., & Ezenwa-Nebife, D. C. (2015). The Impact of Hands-On-Approach on Student Academic Performance in Basic Science and Mathematics. *Higher Education Studies*, 5(6), 47-51.

- x. Ekwueme, C. O., & Meremikwu, A. (2010). The use of calculator in Teaching Calculations in logarithms in secondary schools. *Journal of Issues on mathematics*, 13, 117-118.
- xi. Franklin, S., & Peat, M. (2005). Virtual versus real: an argument for maintaining diversity in the learning environment. *International Journal of Continuing Engineering Education and Life Long Learning* , 15, 67–78.
- xiii. Hidi, S., & Renninger, K. A. (2006). The four-phase model of interest development. *Educational Psychologist* , 41, 111–127.
- xiv. Hurst, O. (2002). How we teach molecular structure to freshmen. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 79(6), 763 – 764.
- xvi. Lebuffe, J. R. (1994). *Hands-on science in the elementary school*. East Lansing, MI: National Center for Research on Teacher Learning (ERIC Document Reproduction Service No. ED 375003).
- xvii. Lee, O., Penfield, R., & Maerten-Rivera, J. (2009). Effects of fidelity of implementation on science achievement gains among English language learners. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 46(7), 826-859.
- xviii. Obanya, P. (2012). *Transformational Pedagogy in Higher Education*. 26th Convocation Lecture of University of Calabar, Nigeria.
- xix. O’Connor J., P. (2002). Teachers are the problem in SMT, not girls. Retrieved January 9, 2009, from <http://www.adea.org>
- xx. Robinson, W. (2003). Chemistry problem-solving: Symbol, macro, micro, and process aspects. *Journal of Chemical Education*(80), 978 – 982.
- xxi. Taber, K. S. (2001). The mismatch between assumed prior knowledge and the learners’ conceptions: A typology of learning impediments. *Educational Studies*, 2(27), 159 – 171.
- xxii. Teichert, M., & Stacy, A. (2002). Promoting understanding of chemical bonding and spontaneity through student explanation and integration of ideas. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 6(39), 464 – 496.

- xxiii. Turpin, T. J. (2000). A study of the effects of an integrated, activity-based science curriculum on student achievement, science process skills, and science attitudes. *Dissertation Abstracts International*, 61(11), 4329A (UMI No. AAT 9993727).
- xxiv. Ünal, S. (2008). Changing students' misconceptions of floating and sinking using hands-on activities. *Journal of Baltic Science Education*, 7(3), 134-146.

Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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